

Comparative Study of New Woman in Manju Kapur's "Difficult Daughters" and Ama Ata Aidoo's "Changes: A Love Story":

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Abstract:

The study of the protagonist's metamorphosis and how it affected their evolution is included because the topic of the book evokes the idea of a new woman. The subject emphasizes women's ongoing battles with various emotions including meekness and repression, as well as their pursuit of freedom and a happy life. We saw how the character perfected themselves through persistent struggle and learned to play the game of life in accordance with their own rules and preferences. They develop into little more than puppets in the hands of the patriarchal society. They demonstrate that they have the power to control their own fate. The current study examines the female protagonists of a selected Manju Kapur and Ama Ata Aidoo novels. They demonstrate their capacity for adaptation and adoption. The study's primary objectives are to explore issues affecting women and to concentrate on the personalities and pursuits of the heroines. We observe that once suppressed and downtrodden women emerge from the patriarchal system, they are better able to make a name for themselves. Beyond all of these roles, Manju Kapur and Ama Ata Aidoo reveal the woman as a self-sufficient person with free will, and we perceive this self-sufficient woman as the embodiment of the new woman. The chosen topic emphasizes the necessity for women to express themselves and speak out against the patriarchal society by encouraging them to break out of their shells. Breaking out from tradition is vital if they want to understand who they are. They must create their own identities in order to become accepted members of society. Manju Kapur and Ama Ata Aidoo consider the complexity of existence, numerous histories, cultures, and value systems in their works. Physical violence and social rejection are inflicted upon their patriarchally influenced and downtrodden women. Their gender causes them to be more prejudiced and discriminatory. But because they do not want to be social rubber dolls, they are always working to establish their identities. The works by these authors mostly explore the subjects of education, marriage, and polygamy. These female authors generally portray the emergence of new women in their works; these "New Women" are the byproducts of the shifting social environment and are persistent in establishing their distinctive presence in the society and nation to which they belong. These women are rather revolutionary, and they use education to showcase their individuality and independence. They have strong opinions and are independent, tenacious, and goal-oriented. The expressions "new woman," "new freedom," and "sexual revolution" all referred to cultural changes that made it possible for young women to leave the Victorian home and enter the previously male-only public sphere. This also caused major emotional issues for women because many of them were unable to manage the new situation or balance their private and public lives in a new and changing society.

Introduction:

What is New Woman:

The late nineteenth-century feminist ideal known as "The New Woman" had a significant impact on feminism far into the twentieth century. In her piece "The New Aspect of the Woman Question," which appeared in the North American Review in March 1894, author Sarah Grand introduced the term "New Woman". Henry James, a British-American author, further popularized the word by using it to characterize the rise in feminism and the emergence of educated, independent career women in both Europe and the United

States. The New Woman stretched society's boundaries, which are largely determined by men. The New Woman desired to be free to go places on her own; traditionally, respectable women were watched over by a guardian or friend of some sort. In view of the increased chances for higher education, women could choose to forego the home sphere that was assigned to them and begin vying for occupations that were previously only held by men. With a job, The New Woman could take charge of her life and decisions because she would no longer need to get married in order to feel secure. The New Woman believed that she could obtain

an education and support herself financially in society without always having to find a husband. The established gender norms were threatened by The New Woman's refusal to bear children and her masculine appearance. It is interesting to note that the New Woman was simultaneously portrayed as non-female, unfeminine, and ultra-feminine. Being thin, mannish, and/or sexy was the most important quality; having strong emotions was considered as questionable. Women changed, but they also gave up their previous domain, the house. If a woman's basic requirements go beyond wanting equality with males, expressing her own individuality, and being conscious of her own rights as a woman—and not as a mother, a wife, or a daughter in law—then she is considered “modern” or “new.” A woman who rebels against authority is not considered a new woman. When the woman evaluates and considers her place in the social, moral, and spiritual spheres, she can be new. Not only new women ponder about these topics and their place in society; occasionally, ordinary women do as well. She begins by considering social, moral, and intellectual issues. The new women consider more than just their place in society; they also consider the part they play in a world where men predominate. She strives to develop her own way of thinking and intellectual capacity. After a protracted exploration of her strong desire to be recognized as an individual with personal autonomy—an independent femininity with a free mind and spirit—the genuine concept of the new woman has emerged. She also fights for the abolition of patriarchal dominance in order to make a difference in society. This study's conception of the new woman is not the study of contemporary or even modern women. The key factors affecting how women define themselves are the complexity of life as well as varied histories, cultures, and values. However, contemporary women aspire to overcome these challenges by possessing some unique qualities, such as equality, uniqueness, etc.

Manju kapur as an Author:

A significant novelist of the twenty-first century is Manju Kapur. She was born on August 6, 1948, in Amritsar. She has experienced difficult times in India. The Miranda House University College for Women is where she received her degree. She then pursued an M.A. at Halifax, Nova

Scotia's Dalhousie University and an M.Phil. at Delhi University. Although she is currently retired from Miranda House, Delhi University, she still teaches English literature there. She began by writing theatre, then poetry. She discovered that writing novels was her strength, and she is now a novelist full-time. Manju Kapur is the author of five novels, including *Custody* (2011), *The Immigrant* (2009), *Home* (2006), and *Difficult Daughters* (1998). Her debut book, *Difficult Daughters*, was widely praised abroad. The Commonwealth Writers Prize for the finest first book was given to this work. In India, it was the best-selling item. *Home* was on the Hutch Crossword Book Award shortlist. Both inside and outside of India, her books have been translated into other languages.

Ama Ata Aidoo As an Author:

Ama Ata Aidoo, a writer from Ghana, was born in 1942. She has written English-language plays, novels, short stories, and poems. Before relocating to Zimbabwe to pursue writing full-time, Aidoo lived and taught in the USA. She was awarded the 1992 Commonwealth Writers Prize for Best Book for her book *Changes* (Africa). The drama *Dilemma of a Ghost* (1956) and the anthology of short stories *No Sweetness Here* are among Ama Ata Aidoo's works (1970). Aidoo didn't publish a lot of material between 1970 and 1985, the year *Someone Talking to Sometime*, a collection of poems, was published. Her later works include the novel *Changes: A Love Story* (1991), the poetry collection *An Angry Letter in January and Other Poems* (1992), the collection of children's stories *The Eagle and the Chickens* (1986), the collection of short stories *The Girl Who Can and Other Stories* (1997), and the collection of short stories *Diplomatic Pounds and Other Stories* (2012).

New Woman in Manju Kapur's "Difficult Daughters":

Manju Kapur's "Difficult Daughters" is based in part on the life of her mother, Virmati, and is set during the struggle for India's freedom. The reader will meet Virmati, a strong and independent woman founded on patriarchal tradition, thanks to Kapur. Although Virmati is intelligent and financially independent, Kapur focuses on the fact that she still experiences hardships as the Professor's second wife. The example of Virmati demonstrates that breaking

patriarchal conventions requires more than just education and financial freedom. One needs resolution and a strong will to declare their self-identity. Virmati's early rejection of her engagement to her fiancé, which she did in opposition to her strict Arya Samaj family, which also included her parents, paternal grandfather, and aunt (the father's sister), is a prime example of her rebellious nature.

Virmati's attitude in this regard fuels her need to carve out a place for herself. According to Kapur's portrayal of Virmati, she is a revolutionary who fights for the right to seek an education and someone who rises to the occasion in challenging situations. Virmati is the start of a "New Woman" since she doesn't want "to be a rubber doll for others to move as they willed" (DD, 85). She overcomes her disappointment by demonstrating an amazing mental fortitude. "Strong to bear the pain, silently, without anyone knowing" (DD, 101). As she destroys the professor's letters, she does so with resolve and unfazedness. It shows her will to end their illicit relationship and look forward to leading a fulfilling life in Lahore. Shakuntala, Virmati's cousin, claims that there is nothing wrong with her and that she is not the kind of girl to abruptly cancel an engagement. There was no way Virmati could be at blame. Virmati did not know what to say "that part of her life was closed. Discussing it brings back the pain" (DD, 115). In Lahore Virmati "... was to be supervised like a jailbird on a parole. Marriage is acceptable to her family, but not independence" (DD 115). However, Virmati's incompatibility is only briefly present, and she is unable to transform into a "New Woman." Although she takes a firm stance against the professor, in Lahore she caves in to his pleading and fervour. Their friendship develops into a passionate one when Harish travels to Lahore with Virmati. The inability of Virmati to adhere to the ingrained social code has caused her to encounter new challenges. Virmati fights to find new ways of living established by colonial patriarchal domination by rejecting the socially prescribed standards for women's behaviour. Her inability to adhere to social norms does not provide her happiness or independence; rather, it leaves her feeling imbalanced and alone, which finally leads to her marriage to Harish, a married man she adores. The best illustration of an influential Indian feminist

who dealt with a specific socio-historical setting is Virmati. Another major setback in her life is the professor's marriage to Virmati, and she now regrets ever getting married to him. She is striving to establish herself as a second wife through modification and compromise after suppressing all of her revolutionary principles. As mentioned by Grewal in "Manju Kapur's Virmati in *Difficult Daughters: A New Woman*", "Thus Virmati dares to cross one patriarchal threshold, she is caught into another, where her free spirit is curbed and all she does is adjust, compromise and adapt. She is a loser whose acts totally alienate her from her family and her fails to create a space for herself for whom she had been striving all alone" (Grewal, 60). Virmati decided to pretend to be a second wife in order to avoid social stigma associated with having a child before marriage. She chooses to renounce her status as a revolutionary woman in favour of taking on the role of a wife who asks her husband for permission. She is completely cut off from her family as a result of Virmati's activities, and she is unable to carve out the space for herself for which she has been striving on her own. She is now comfortable with her status as a "second wife," which is acceptable in Indian custom, rather than continuing her relationship with Harish that they had before they got married. She continues going back to the outdated social norms, masculine dominance, and outdated views. Virmati locks herself up voluntarily because she lacks "resistance". She can fight against her society and family, but she can't fight against Harish's love. She was marginalised forever after losing her identity somewhere in her marital house. The female heroines of Manju Kapur's works do not develop into new women in the traditional sense despite receiving education and independence. Their free souls are restrained and all they can do is "adjust, compromise, and adapt" even though they dare to breach one patriarchal threshold and are then snared by another. She depicts the constantly evolving image of women in her works, one that is shifting away from the stereotypical image of enduring, selfless women and toward one of ambitious, dependent women. The concept of new women in Indian society or for Indian society is completely different from the one in the west. Her female characters defy

conventional morality and move toward modernism and novelty in her stories. Manju Kapur aims to express her own wish for the development of new women in reality through the characters she creates.

New Woman in Ama Ata Aidoo's "Changes: A Love Story":

Esi was a protagonist of the *Changes*. She is an ideal epitome of New Woman. She should have shown some patience in circumstance which comes in her family life. After her marriage to Oko, Esi "Definitely put her career well above any duties she owed as a wife." She "complained" constantly every time she had to walk into the kitchen. She claims that the reason she left Oko is that she lacks personal time. Even when Ali offers her a lot of alone time, she still has a problem and constantly laments the attention Oko provided her but that she wasted. While Esi ends up with an unofficial divorce in her first marriage and an official divorce in a second marriage because she was unable to manage her marriage properly and in other side Fusena had to deal with a polygamous husband. Fusena and Opokuya, who also resemble new women in *Changes* to some extent, are likewise playing the roles of mothers and trying to maintain their filial lives at the same time. According to the description, Fusena is a primary school instructor who has completed a postsecondary teacher preparation course. Her schooling came very close to securing her a marriage and a job that may have given her financial independence. The contradictory aspect of it is "that the few men who claim they like intelligent and active women are also interested in having such women permanently in their beds and in their kitchens." (*Changes* 54) It appears in the conversation between Esi and Opokuya. The smart ladies that men meet and fall in love with are sharp because, among other things, they have hard occupations in stimulating environments, according to Aidoo. Few men are aware of this, though. Some of these individuals are unwilling to acknowledge the challenging tasks that go along with these fascinating occupations. These kinds of labour keep a woman's mind active and interested. Aidoo adds that: "the first thing a man who marries a woman mainly for the quickness of her brain tries to do is to get her to change her job to a more reasonable one...and then the more reasonable job, is

often quite dull too." Naturally, the intent behind this assertion is to maintain the woman in the conventional role associated with womanhood. The woman will be judged for being stupid and lacking in intelligence because of this entrenched position, which is incredibly difficult to swallow. (or, satisfying a man's appetite and urges to procreate.) Again, the able-bodied woman who must change her posture in this fashion usually feels unfulfilled, bored, and unhappy. Exactly the same thing occurred to Fusena after she wed Ali. Fusena appears to have been persuaded by Ali to utilize her intelligence and resourcefulness to care for herself and their unborn child while he was away. It's noteworthy that Fusena's schooling did not completely free her. She benefited economically from it, but she wasn't content with it. As indicated by the fact that he later wed a different woman with a master's degree and added his assistant, Ali believed that education and an enterprising bride were no panacea for adultery. The pitiful way in which Fusena's character is described precludes readers from seeing her as a wonderful role model for women, despite the fact that she is in some respects depicted as a new woman. She is portrayed as a strong woman who manages her polygamous husband and her new profession, but she is not elevated since she is angry because her husband chose a lady with more education to be above her and she was powerless to stop it. Opokuya, on the other hand, manages her marriage despite the challenging circumstances. Opokuya is portrayed by the narrator as more of a stereotypically strong female figure on this particular note. Because she stands up against injustice and refuses to let being called "fat" make her feel inferior, Opokuya is strong. "She had been a state registered nurse and a qualified mid-wife, for nearly fifteen years" (*Changes*, 18). The narrator describes Opokuya as "certainly overweight" and notes that she is heavier than Esi. She couldn't care less. Every day of the year, she laughed and was nimble on her feet. She made it pretty clear every time the matter of her weight came up that the reason, she was overweight had nothing to do with her lack of understanding on how to deal with it. Esi and Opokuya, two African women, are contrasted in this passage. The idea is to show how Opokuya continues to stand out for her open-minded view on

African women whereas Esi, despite her high social rank, suffers from her rigid, westernized lifestyle. Opokuya had decided she wanted four children for herself. She talked about the matter with her husband Kubi after having them. Even with reference to herself, Opokuya had yet to find a neat solution to the weight problem. Sometimes she would say that she was a bit worried about the possibility of a cardiac problem. She regularly checked her blood pressure, and it remained unexpectedly normal. In addition, she had long ago decided that she could live without the more obvious illegal goods like sugar and fatty foods because she didn't know how far her body could expand. So it was that knowledge and this discipline which gave her the confidence to argue hotly. (Changes, 16) The narrator accepts and embraces Opokuya's character as the appropriate woman whose character is admirable, despite the fact that it is difficult to live in the kind of patriarchal culture present in Aidoo's *Changes*. Although not all of the New Women disapproved of motherhood, many did because it was thought that having children and rearing them would keep a woman at home. These were just a few of the attributes that made up the New Woman and the Victorian ideal of femininity, but the meticulously made moulds that women had been shaped into was starting to fall apart. Because of her ability to live harmoniously with her husband and four children, the narrative voice supports Opokuya's character. It is important to note that Opokuya chooses to buy her own car despite a severe disagreement over the use of their car in order to restore harmony in her household. She embodies the Stivanist's thesis that "African women are indissolubly tied with men and so must seek out ways of coexisting happily and amicably with men". It is advantageous when a woman's salary enables her to make such a significant decision to bring peace into her home. This is made feasible by the economy of Opokuya's independence. She might be able to achieve this financial freedom by furthering her education.

Comparative Aspect:

Manju Kapur and Ama Ata Aidoo are two female writers who critique the phallogocentric patriarchal culture in a feminocentric approach through their

literature. The patriarchal society imposes numerous limitations on women. They provide strong female characters like Virmati, Astha, Esi, Opokuya, and Fusena the ability to vehemently challenge patriarchy by disregarding social norms. They choose this peculiar route in order to live and discover more about themselves. They are able to satisfy their own needs as a result, leading to psychological independence. They introduce a New Woman figure that is self-conscious, educated, aware of her surroundings, and somewhat driven to build a life for herself. In the patriarchal system, women's roles and the teaching of their sex roles are very well defined. Any departure from this assigned task is frowned upon and may result in severe repercussions. It is believed that all deviant sexual behaviour goes against nature and must be stopped. These authors contend that rather than biological causes, women's oppression has cultural origins. In this circumstance, it would be fair to refer to them as "culturally marginalized women." The traditional approach has long forced women to live in abject poverty. As soon as adolescents become aware of their brewing rebellious tendencies, they feel guilty. This sense of mental servitude and subordination is one of the key reasons women are less progressed than men. A conflict of the sexes or unreasonable responses between them are not necessary for women to have a respected place in society. With proper grooming and a positive view on life, you can address this psychological condition. This appears to be the common theme in all of the literature by women, regardless of where they are from. Modern women are more aware of their potential and are able to keep up with the fast-changing standards of living on a mental and physical level. Her journey, however, cannot be finished without the support of her companion's friendship. Women in the modern or new era recognized the value of individualism and the necessity of rebelling against societal norms or taboos. One must first understand the traditional woman's life in order to understand the function of the new woman in society, as one cannot understand the new woman's function without first understanding the traditional woman. The novels of Kapur and Aidoo significantly influenced postmodern English literature. Realistic portrayals of the

characters show how they reflect contemporary culture. They have given consideration to the requirements, disputes, and survival of women. The parallels between Manju Kapur's and Ama Ata Aidoo's works demonstrate that the need to understand the past in order to understand the present is more than just a sentimental goal; rather, it suggests that the problem of how to maintain generational continuity in a contemporary environment seems to exist in a field without boundaries. In terms of marriage, Kapur has proven to be accommodative. Even when her female characters in marriage suffer, they continue the marriage-based bond. After marriage, Virmati of *Difficult Daughters* encounters challenges as the second wife of a professor. Despite this, she maintains her marriage, accepts her circumstances, and ultimately finds happiness. In Aidoo's work, the main characters take risky actions both before and after getting married. They choose the partner themselves. Because they want freedom, they don't hesitate to end their marriages. Realistic characters have been developed by Aidoo and Kapur, respectively. The strong and independent women in Kapur's stories. Aidoo has also developed characters who are confident and strong. The characters in Kapur's books are well-educated, employed, and financially secure. The apparent reasons for the bolder behaviour of Aidoo's female protagonists are their education, freedom, and mobility. Despite all obstacles, Kapur's heroines manage to keep their relationship going. They have given up on their desire to live with their husband and family. The heroines of Aidoo's leave their husbands as soon as things get too bad. Because Kapur's literature portrays the crises of the modern man in India, readers may identify with and relate to these everyday struggles when they read it. Aidoo has essentially depicted the New Woman in Ghanaian society. She also emphasized modern topics such as psychiatric problems, women's freedom of sex, and other facets of contemporary life.

In the rigidly organized and tradition-bound civilizations of Ghana and India, women suffer the most because social conventions and moral codes have been constructed in a way that is especially damaging to them. This is possibly the reason why Indian and Ghanaian female

novelists, who are also influenced by their historical and cultural context, continue to address the feminist phenomenon in their fictional works by depicting Indian and Ghanaian women whose lot has been to endure repression from the authorities in silence for a very long time. Because of their high intellectual accomplishments and command of modern sciences, particularly psychology, these novelists fully concentrate on the suffering of their characters and put their private lives and social constraints in perspective. Their naturally feminine sensitivity gives their writings a sympathetic tone and a psychological depth that complement their observations.

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